

A CHAIN OF FACTORS AFFECTING THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION, WAYS TO ELIMINATE THEM

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Annotation. In this article, one of the important issues in the education system is the topic of negative factors affecting the quality of education and the ways to eliminate them. The fact that the quality of education depends on the management process is shown by the example of necessary materials.

Key words: Negative education, lesson, schools, activity, management, competence

Improving the quality of education is important in the development of any country, because if there is development in education, there will be development in every field. Based on the needs of the participants of the educational process in the continuous education system, as well as the needs of science, education, production, preschool education, general secondary education, which are considered the main components of the continuous education system in the preparation of competitive graduates, selection of technologies that increase the effectiveness of educational processes in accordance with the integrative nature of secondary vocational education, higher education, post-higher education, out-of-school education and retraining and qualification processes, as well as pedagogic Studying the problems that arise in the processes and developing mechanisms for their elimination is one of the most important requirements of today. Currently, various and wide-ranging innovations are introduced in the field of education. The public education system is the main link of the education sector.

Currently, the use of pedagogical innovations in the educational process is a global trend of world development. This, in turn, requires paying special attention to the systematic introduction of innovations into the field of education at the same time due to the rapid development of the modernization process in the country. However, the level of implementation of pedagogical scientific research on the introduction of new content, form, and method of teaching in this field cannot be considered sufficient for now.

To reduce the existing problems in the field of education, to increase the quality of education, to adapt the knowledge and professional skills of

pedagogues to the requirements of the time, to use innovative educational technologies in teaching, to improve the effectiveness of the organized lessons, and to improve the pedagogy of each subject for the student to master well. and it is required to ensure the transfer of information using technologies. Implementation of education based on the competency approach in teaching is one of the urgent issues of students being able to apply their knowledge in life, choosing a profession, getting independent education, and developing academic competences.

Reforms in the field of education are carried out mainly on the basis of person-oriented education. It is proved that the knowledge of the student who understands the basics of the subject is the real knowledge, not the education based on memorization as before. It is our main goal that students and young students should be able to apply the knowledge they have learned not only by memorization, but we are working to achieve it. It is not for nothing that specialized schools and private schools are being established for this purpose. Great attention is paid to the organization of educational processes based on STEAM educational technology. At the time when we are paying attention to high-quality education in the education system of our country, the existing problems in the field of education are an obstacle to this, for example, we can say the following;

- lack of systematic and innovative activities in the implementation of creative ideas of talented young people in strengthening the theoretical and practical knowledge of learners;
- that pedagogues do not organize educational sessions aimed at developing the intellectual abilities of students;
- lack of widespread implementation of innovative pedagogical technologies and methods by pedagogues;
- mutual cooperation between educational institutions is not fully established;
- the fact that it is limited to the repetition of information, that it is not at the level of demand;
- the need to update and change the structure of educational programs;
- the need to include mechanisms for designing the educational process;
- lack of correct interpretation of pedagogical and information technologies and independent education;
- issues of proper communication with parents of school teachers;
- existing problems in the education and upbringing process;
- insufficient material and technical base;

- the need to include mechanisms for designing the educational process;
- incorrect interpretation of pedagogical and information technologies and independent education;
- issues of proper communication with parents of school teachers;
- existing problems in the joint conduct of the education and upbringing process;
- lack of experience in young specialist personnel:
- a number of problems, such as school attendance issues, are being considered and various decisions are being made to eliminate them.

Forming the knowledge and skills of schoolchildren, educating them in the spirit of loyalty to national and universal values, increasing the prestige of the teaching profession and the quality of pedagogues, improving textbooks and educational methodical complexes based on the requirements of the times, bringing school educational institutions to international standards. in order to establish responsive modern models, as well as in accordance with the state program for the implementation of the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026: - to increase the prestige of the teaching profession in society, to create favorable social conditions for pedagogues and to give them a decent incentive for their work encourage;

- to increase the responsibility of teachers in providing education and training to young people, their demand for continuous professional development;
- formation of national personnel reserves for general secondary educational institutions, development of criteria for advanced school principals and exemplary teachers, and based on them, evaluating the activities of leaders and pedagogues;
- systematic organization of spiritual and educational work in general secondary educational institutions, establishment of continuous monitoring, assessment and forecasting mechanisms in this direction, family, especially father, in child education and upbringing - increasing the position of the mother;
- activities such as meaningful organization of students' free time, improvement of the system of directing them to professions are being carried out.

The future of the country is in the hands of young people. Only educated and talented young people can create a bright future country, take a leading position in any field, raise the flag of our country to the world arena. It will be effective only if we give quality and reasonable education to young people, who can not only recite them by heart, but also apply them in practice. The choice of teachers is very important. Every pedagogue should be passionate about his profession and have sufficient knowledge and skills. Each training session

should be directed to the formation of educational and cognitive competencies in students, to independently find the necessary information from the educational literature. The quality of the training is determined by the pedagogue's responsible approach to the subject being read and analyzed, his skill in conveying its content to the students, and the methodical activity of organizing and managing the training based on today's requirements. The teacher will have achieved a certain goal if he can explain that the topic is based on an important theory and that the ideas are logically connected. For this, it is necessary to use the possibilities of modern teaching technologies.

Eliminating the existing shortcomings and problems in improving the quality of education, clearly defining goals and tasks in this way, using world-recognized experiences for this purpose, using information technologies in combination with pedagogical technologies will improve the quality of professional training of future specialists. serves to improve, it increases the efficiency of the process. Clarification of educational goals, use of various technologies and methods used in teaching and mastering processes, focusing on content leads to the development and improvement of the activities of educational institutions.

In conclusion, we also consider it useful to use the opportunity of professors-educators working or studying in higher education institutions abroad. We think that it is necessary to use the experience of the leading higher educational institutions of the Republic and to appoint scientific supervisors from among the professors-teachers of these higher educational institutions in organizing the preparation of talented students for writing graduation theses. In order to increase the number of foreign students studying in the higher educational institutions of our republic, information about educational programs taught in Russian, English and other foreign languages, as well as about admission, living conditions, contracts, etc., will be posted on their websites. we recommend posting data. In the future, one-year Uzbek language courses should be organized for them. In our opinion, the above-mentioned opinions allow to improve the quality of education in higher educational institutions, at least partially.

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